

Figure S1

Supplementary Figure 1. Integrated single-cell sequencing populations from human and pig PBMCs, related to Figure 1.

(A) Correlation analysis of expression levels of homologous genes between human and pig. (B) UMAP visualization of human-pig integrated scRNA-seq data divided into 38 color-labeled groups at 1 resolution. (C) Correlation analysis of human and pig cell types.

Figure S2

Supplementary Figure 2. Differentially expressed genes in human and pig myeloid cells, related to Figure 3.

(A) Gene expression profile of myeloid populations, including CD14⁺ monocytes, CD16⁺ monocytes, monocyte-derived DCs and pDCs. The color scale indicates the level of gene expression. Red represents relatively high expression, and blue represents relatively low expression. (B) Genes differentially expressed between humans and pigs in pDCs, as presented by heatmap. (C) Dot plot showing DEGs between humans and pigs in monocyte-derived DCs. (D) Genes differentially expressed between humans and pigs in CD14⁺ monocytes, as presented by heatmap.

Figure S3

Supplementary Figure 3. Integrated single-cell sequencing populations from human and pig T cells, related to Figure 4.

(A) UMAP visualization of human-pig T cells from integrated scRNA-seq as divided into 13 color-labeled groups. (B) Specific T cell markers presented in violin plots, with colors labeling different clusters. (C) UMAP visualization of human-pig integrated clustering for T cells. Different colors label different clusters. (D) UMAP visualization of separated human cells (left) and pig cells (right) for T cells. Different colors label different clusters.

Figure S4

Supplementary Figure 4. Marker gene expression in $\alpha\beta$ T cell populations defined from human-pig integrated scRNA-seq, related to Figure 4.

Gene expression of *CCR7*, *SELL*, *CD4*, *CD8A*, *CD40LG*, *GZMK*, *PRF1* and *GNLY* in human and pig scRNA-seq data. The red scale in the UMAP plot indicates the gene expression level in human, and the blue scale in the UMAP plot indicates the gene expression level in pig.

Figure S5

Supplementary Figure 5. Differentially expressed genes in human and pig $\alpha\beta$ T cell populations, related to Figure 4.

(A) Bar graphs showing DEG numbers for 6 $\alpha\beta$ T cell populations between human and pig. (B) Genes differentially expressed between naïve CD8⁺ T cells in human and pig, as presented by heatmap. (C) Genes differentially expressed between naïve CD4⁺ T cells in human and pig, as presented by heatmap. (D) Genes differentially expressed between GZMK⁺ CD4 T cells in human and pig, as presented by heatmap. (E) Genes differentially expressed between GZMK⁺ CD8 T cells in human and pig, as presented by heatmap.

Figure S6

A

B

Supplementary Figure 6. Developmental trajectories of $\gamma\delta$ T cells, related to Figure 6.

(A) Gene expression levels are shown for the trajectory. (B) Gene expression kinetics along pseudotime progression for representative genes in human (left) and pig (right). Solid lines represent pre-branch to cell fate 1, and dotted lines represent pre-branch to cell fate 2.

Figure S7

Supplementary Figure 7. Gene Ontology (GO) functional annotation of DEGs over pseudotime from pre-branch to cell fate 1 and from pre-branch to cell fate 2 in human and pig, related to Figure 7.

(A-C) Bubble charts showing GO terms for genes up-regulated in pre-branch (A), genes up-regulated in cell fate 1 (B), and genes up-regulated in cell fate 2 (C).

Figure S8

Supplementary Figure 8. Gene expression patterns of B cells, related to Figure 7.

Gene expression kinetics along pseudotime progression for representative genes in human (left) and pig (right). Solid lines represent pre-branch to cell fate 1, and dotted lines represent pre-branch to cell fate 2.

Figure S9

A

B

Supplementary Figure 9. Characterization of CD24⁺ B cells, related to Figure 7.

(A) Gene expression of *BATF*, *IRF5*, and *TBX21* in pig B cell subsets, as visualized by UMAP. The brown scale indicates the level of gene expression in pig cells. (B) Heatmap of the mean transcriptome showing genes that are highly expressed in CD24⁺ B cells. Color gradient represents gene expression level.